

THERMOELASTIC COUPLING IN GRAPHITE-EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The use of uncoupled theory in thermal stress analysis of traditional structural materials is usually permissible because the effect of thermoelastic coupling is rather small in most cases. However, this effect may be significant in composites, although to date, it has not been fully investigated. In this paper, the effect of thermoelastic coupling in the evaluation of transient temperature fields in an orthotropic layer is studied. The coupled finite element formulation of the thermoelastic equations for an orthotropic material is derived, and the resulting code is validated by performing an analysis on a simple isotropic problem for which the analytical solution is known. The analysis is repeated for a layer of unidirectional graphite-epoxy material, incorporating experimental data on the dependence of the thermal expansion coefficients on temperature available in the literature. It is shown that there are significant differences in the prediction of temperature fields by the coupled and uncoupled equations.

KEYWORDS: Thermoelasticity; Coupling; Transient; Composites; Finite elements.

1. INTRODUCTION

Structural components made of composite materials are frequently expected to operate at elevated or low temperatures. Whilst it is generally accepted that in most thermal stress applications involving metals the thermoelastic coupling term can be neglected without introducing significant errors, the same may not be true for composite materials. A survey of the literature, however, indicates that very little work has been done in the area of transient thermal stress analysis in composite structures [1]. This is partly due to the fact that these problems are usually analytically intractable and recourse is often sought in numerical procedures such as the finite difference and finite element methods. However, most commercially available finite element packages handle only uncoupled transient heat conduction problems. Furthermore, it is well-known that moisture ingress and temperature arising from adverse environmental conditions can significantly affect the mechanical properties of certain composite materials such as carbon fibre-reinforced plastics [1,2,3]. The temperature dependence of these properties should be taken into account in a proper analysis of the coupled transient problems [4]. In this paper, a study on the coupled and uncoupled transient temperature fields in an orthotropic media by the finite element method is carried out, using values of expansion coefficients published in the literature [5,6].

2. FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

The differential equation for thermal-mechanical coupling in elastic solids [3] in the absence of moisture can be written as

$$-h_{i,i} = \rho C_v \dot{T} - \left(C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl} - (\beta_{ij} (T - T_0))_{,T} \right) T \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where $h_{i,i}$ is the rate of heat flux, ρ is the density, C_v is the specific heat capacity, C_{ijkl} are elements of the stiffness matrix, ϵ_{ij} are the strains, β_{ij} are material coefficients related to thermal expansion, T is the absolute temperature and T_0 is the absolute reference temperature. The subscript $_{,i}$ denotes the partial derivative $\partial/\partial x_i$, the subscript $_{,T}$ denotes $\partial/\partial T$ and $\dot{}$ denotes the derivative with respect to time.

The second term on the right hand side of equation (1) describes the contribution of changing material properties with respect to temperature and is neglected in classical thermoelastic theory. It is clearly seen that if Fourier's Law of heat conduction applies, and all material properties are independent of temperature, then equation (1) reduces to the well-known classical solution

$$-h_{i,i} = \rho C_v \dot{T} + T \beta_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } h_i = -k_{ij} T_{,i} \quad (3)$$

and k_{ij} are the thermal conductivities. Furthermore, if the temperature changes considered are small in comparison to the reference absolute temperature T_0 , it is usual [7] to replace T in the second term of equation (2) by T_0 :

$$-h_{i,i} = \rho C_v \dot{T} + T_0 \beta_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \quad (4)$$

In the case of uncoupled theory, the second term in equation (2) is ignored. We define the quantity

$$\theta = T - T_0 \quad (5)$$

Multiplying both sides of equation (4) by θ , we obtain

$$-\theta h_{i,i} = \theta \rho C_v \dot{T} + \theta T_0 \beta_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \quad (6)$$

The quantity on the left hand side can be expressed as

$$-\theta h_{i,i} = -(\theta h_i)_{,i} + h_i \theta_{,i}$$

so that for the entire solid,

$$-\int_V \theta h_{i,i} dv = -\int_V (\theta h_i)_{,i} dv + \int_V h_i \theta_{,i} dv \quad (7)$$

On application of the Gauss-Green theorem, we have

$$-\int_V \theta h_{i,i} dv = \int_V h_i \theta_{,i} dv - \int_S \theta h_i n_i ds \quad (8)$$

where n_i is the outward normal to the surface s .

Substitution of equations (3) and (6) into (8) yields

$$\int_V \theta (\rho C_v \dot{\theta} + T_0 \beta_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}) dv = -\int_V k_{ij} \theta_{,i} \theta_{,j} dv - \int_S \theta h_i n_i ds \quad (9)$$

For small displacements, the strain vector ϵ may be related to the displacement vector u by the relationship

$$\epsilon = Bu \quad (10)$$

where $\varepsilon = \{\varepsilon_{11} \ \varepsilon_{22} \ \varepsilon_{33} \ \gamma_{12} \ \gamma_{31} \ \gamma_{23}\}^T$ and $u = \{u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3\}^T$. The matrix B is defined as

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} \partial/\partial x_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \partial/\partial x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \partial/\partial x_3 \\ \partial/\partial x_2 & \partial/\partial x_1 & 0 \\ \partial/\partial x_3 & 0 & \partial/\partial x_1 \\ 0 & \partial/\partial x_3 & \partial/\partial x_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The displacements and temperature at any point within an element can be expressed in terms of the nodal values:

$$u = Nu_n \quad (12)$$

$$\theta = M\theta_n \quad (13)$$

where u_n and θ_n are the vectors of nodal displacements and nodal temperatures, respectively. N and M are the prescribed shape functions. Substitution of equations (10) to (13) into (9) results in the following expression:

$$-\theta_n^T C \dot{\theta}_n - \theta_n^T L^T \dot{u}_n - \theta_n^T K_c \theta_n - \theta_n^T q = 0$$

$$\text{or} \quad -C \dot{\theta}_n - L^T \dot{u}_n - K_c \theta_n - q = 0 \quad (14)$$

where

$$C = \int_v M^T (\rho C_v / T_0) M \, dv \quad (15)$$

$$K_c = \int_v M^T B'^T (K_k / T_0) B' M \, dv \quad (16)$$

$$q = \int_v h^T n \theta \, ds \quad (17)$$

$$L = \int_v N^T B'^T D_\theta M \, dv \quad (18)$$

$$K_k = \begin{bmatrix} k_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & k_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$B' = \begin{bmatrix} \partial/\partial x_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \partial/\partial x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \partial/\partial x_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$D_\theta = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \beta_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

Equation (14) leads to the recurrence relation between the time interval $t-\Delta t$ to t :

$$-L^T (u_{nt} - u_{n(t-\Delta t)}) - (K_c m \Delta t + C) \theta_{nt} - ((1-m)K_c \Delta t - C) \theta_{n(t-\Delta t)} = q \quad (22)$$

The system is unconditionally stable if the parameter $m \geq 1/2$. In this paper m is chosen to be $1/2$, resulting in the expression

$$-L^T (u_{nt} - u_{n(t-\Delta t)}) - \left(\frac{1}{2}K_c \Delta t + C\right) \theta_{nt} - \left(\frac{1}{2}K_c \Delta t - C\right) \theta_{n(t-\Delta t)} = q \quad (23)$$

The First Law of Thermodynamics states that

$$\dot{K}_e + \dot{E}_e = P + \dot{Q} \quad (24)$$

where

\dot{K}_e = Rate of change of kinetic energy. For the quasi-static case considered here, it can be neglected.

\dot{Q} = Rate of total heat supplied, which is the sum of the heat flux and the internal heat generation.

\dot{E}_e = Rate of change of internal energy, which can be expressed as the sum of \dot{Q} and the stress power, i.e.

$$\dot{E}_e = \dot{Q} + \int_V \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} dv \quad (25)$$

P = The mechanical power developed by surface tractions F_{Ti} and body forces F_{Bi} , given by

$$P = \int_S F_{Ti} \dot{u}_i ds + \int_V F_{Bi} \dot{u}_i dv \quad (26)$$

Hence equation (24) can be written as

$$\int_V \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} dv = \int_S F_{Ti} \dot{u}_i ds + \int_V F_{Bi} \dot{u}_i dv \quad (27)$$

If the material is assumed to be linear Hookean, the relationship

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl} - \beta_{ij} \theta \quad (28)$$

may be substituted into equation (27) to yield

$$\int_V \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl} dv - \int_V \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \beta_{ij} \theta dv - \int_S F_{Ti} \dot{u}_i ds - \int_V F_{Bi} \dot{u}_i dv = 0 \quad (29)$$

Substitution of equations (10) - (13) into (29) results in the expression

$$\dot{u}_n^T K u_n - \dot{u}_n^T L \theta_n - \dot{u}_n^T f = 0$$

or

$$K u_n - L \theta_n = f \quad (30)$$

where

$$K = \int_V N^T B^T D B N dv \quad (31)$$

and

$$f = \int_V N^T F_B dv + \int_S N^T F_T ds \quad (32)$$

D is the material stiffness matrix, and F_B and F_T are the body and traction force vectors, respectively.

For the coupled system, equations (23) and (30) must be solved simultaneously for each time step:

$$\begin{bmatrix} K & -L \\ -L^T & -\left(C + \frac{1}{2} K_c \Delta t\right) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_n \\ \theta_n \end{Bmatrix}_t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ -L^T & -\left(C - \frac{1}{2} K_c \Delta t\right) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_n \\ \theta_n \end{Bmatrix}_{(t-\Delta t)} + \begin{Bmatrix} f \\ q \end{Bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

3. CODE VALIDATION

The formulation described by equation (33) is encoded for a two-dimensional eight-noded plane strain element. The problem chosen to validate the code is that of one-dimensional heat conduction in an isotropic solid, as shown in Fig. 1. A layer of thermoelastic material is bounded by a free surface at $z = h$ and the boundary at $z = 0$ is completely insulated and restrained. A constant temperature θ is maintained at the free surface. This problem is chosen because analytical solutions for both the uncoupled and coupled cases

are known [8,9]. The finite element model used is shown in Fig. 2. It consists of six elements, with the nodes along the boundaries AC and BD restrained from moving in the y direction. Nodes along CD are completely restrained and insulated, and a constant temperature is applied to nodes along AB.

Fig.1 One-dimensional heat conduction through a layer of thermoelastic material.

Fig.2 Finite element mesh.

The solution for the uncoupled case can be presented as a series of temperature isochrones as shown in Fig. 3. The analytical solution from refs. 8 and 9 is represented by the solid curves and is compared to the solution from the finite element model described in Fig. 2. The non-dimensionalized time τ is defined by

$$\tau = \frac{kt}{h^2} \tag{34}$$

where k is the thermal conductivity of the isotropic material.

A measure of thermoelastic coupling in isotropic solids can be indicated by the non-dimensional parameter

$$\delta = 1 + \frac{E(1+\nu)\alpha^2}{(1-2\nu)(1-\nu)\rho C_V T_0} \tag{35}$$

where E is the Young's modulus, ν the Poisson ratio and α the thermal expansion coefficient. It is seen that for the uncoupled case, $\delta = 1$. Fig. 4 shows the analytical and finite element solutions for the coupled case where $\delta = 2$. The analytical curves shown are taken from ref. 8. The choice of $\delta = 2$ here is not intended to reflect the properties of real conventional structural materials, but to enable validation of the finite element code. Indeed, for most conventional materials, δ is very close to unity and in many cases uncoupled theory can be employed with sufficient accuracy.

It can be seen that the finite element solutions agree very well with the analytical solutions for both coupled and uncoupled cases.

Fig.3 Temperature isochrones for uncoupled heat conduction ($\delta = 1$).

Fig.4 Temperature isochrones for coupled heat conduction ($\delta = 2$).

4. APPLICATION TO ORTHOTROPIC MEDIUM

In order to investigate the effect of thermoelastic coupling in composites, the isotropic material properties of the thermoelastic layer in the problem defined in Figures 1 and 2 are replaced by typical orthotropic values for unidirectional T300/5208 given in Table 1 [10]. In Figure 1, the 1-direction in the material coordinate system corresponds to the fibre or longitudinal direction and coincides with the z-direction of the global coordinate system. The 2-direction corresponds to the transverse direction.

Table 1

Longitudinal elastic modulus E_{11} (GPa)	181
Transverse elastic modulus E_{22} (GPa)	10
Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	0.28
Shear modulus G_{12} (GPa)	7.2
Density ρ (g/cm^3)	1.6
Longitudinal conductivity k_{11} (W/m/K)	4.62
Transverse conductivity k_{22} (W/m/K)	0.72

The thermal expansion coefficients of unidirectional T300/5208 graphite epoxy have been experimentally determined by several investigators, notably by Springer [5] and Hyer [6]. Their results are reproduced here in Figures 5 and 6 for reference. Clearly the transverse expansion coefficient α_2 exhibits a strong dependence on temperature and varies by a few thousand microstrains within a modest temperature range. On the other hand, changes in the longitudinal expansion coefficient α_1 with respect to temperature are

relatively small, in the order of only tens of microstrains. Hence α_2 can be expected to play a significant role in the thermoelastic coupling effect. Indeed, Figure 7 shows the influence of different values of α_2 on the solution of the transient temperature distributions. The coupled solutions do not deviate significantly from the uncoupled solution for values of α_2 less than 500 microstrains.

Fig.5 Transverse and longitudinal thermal expansion coefficients from ref. 5.

Fig.6 Transverse thermal expansion coefficients from ref. 6.

Since α_2 is strongly dependent on temperature, a more realistic analysis should include this dependency in the finite element code. The curve described in Figure 6 is used and the coupling matrix L in equation 33 is updated for each time increment. Figure 8 shows the results for two cases of constant surface temperatures ($\theta_s = 50^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\theta_s = 80^{\circ}\text{C}$). Although these surface temperatures are not considered very high, it can be seen that the differences between the coupled and uncoupled solutions become more pronounced with increasing time. Indeed, the maximum difference in the computed temperatures for the case $\theta_s = 80^{\circ}\text{C}$ (at $\tau = 0.5$ and $z/h = 0$) is about 15%. Obviously, the differences can be expected to be even more significant for surface temperatures much higher than those considered in this example.

Fig.7 Transient temperature isochrones for various constant values of α_2 .

Fig.8 Transient temperature isochrones with α_2 varying with temperature.

5. CONCLUSION

The finite element formulation of the coupled thermoelastic equations for an anisotropic body has been derived. The resulting two-dimensional code for plane strain elements has been validated by the analysis of a simple isotropic problem. The analysis is extended to the case of a layer of unidirectional graphite-epoxy material subjected to a constant surface temperature on one side and insulated on the other. Experimentally determined values of the thermal expansion coefficients from the literature indicate that there is a strong but almost linear dependence of the transverse expansion coefficient on temperature. Results of the finite element analysis indicate that the thermoelastic coupling effect is significant for values of the transverse expansion coefficient greater than about 500 microstrains. Analysis incorporating the dependence of the transverse expansion coefficient on temperature suggests that even for moderate temperature changes, there can be significant differences between the coupled and uncoupled solutions. Future work will concentrate on the three-dimensional coupled analysis of stress and temperature fields in laminated composites.

6. REFERENCES

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